

FLOW DISTRIBUTION ANALYSIS OF A NOVEL FCC SYSTEM THROUGH EXPERIMENT STUDY AND ATOMIC MODEL

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Abstract

As the largest palm oil producer in the world, Indonesia has a promising potential to produce green fuel through the Fluid Catalytic Cracking (FCC) process. A novel FCC configuration, FCC Proto X 3, which combines a riser reactor and downer reactor in the system, has been developed. However, several valves including in the FCC system remain a black box to the flow distribution in the system. The objective of this paper is to investigate the effect of the valve setting variation on the airflow distribution of the FCC system. The methodology uses experiment and acausal modeling. The effect of valve setting variation on pressure and average velocity of the airflow has been investigated. The experiment is conducted under cold test conditions, while the acausal model of the FCC system is built by using OpenModelica. It is obtained that valve 2 which controls the flow at the channel toward the regenerator is essential due to its role in controlling the air supply combustion process in the regenerator and driving the spent catalyst particles to the regenerator. Valve 3 is responsible for controlling the flow toward the riser reactor directly. Later, it is responsible for supplying the lifting fluid to support the catalytic cracking reaction at the riser sections. Valve 4 contributes to controlling the lifting fluid to the downer reactor. It will also be responsible for supplying thermal energy from the high-temperature particle catalyst to the reactor. When all valves toward the regenerator and reactor are 100 % open, the measured average velocity at the flue gas outlet and the product outlet are 8.04 m/s and 5.775 m/s respectively. The result shows that the airflow at the FCC system tends to flow through the regenerator. The atomic model estimation also shows a similar trend to the experiment result.

Keywords: Flow distribution, Fluid Catalytic Cracking, Atomic Model, Open Modelica.

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1. Introduction

Climate change remains a critical global issue nowadays. The greenhouse gas emission (GHG) should be suppressed to control the increase in the average global temperature. Through the Paris Agreement, the increase in global temperature should be maintained at less than 2 °C [1]. Reducing the use of fossil fuels and escalating the use of renewable energy would effectively reduce GHG emissions [2, 3]. Most countries around the world now are attempting to reduce GHG emissions [4], including developing countries and tropical countries.

Recently, Indonesia still highly relies on fossil fuels [5, 6]. In 2018, it is documented that most of the energy production in Indonesia is derived from coal and crude oil [5]. On the other hand, the government's goal is to realize the use of renewable energy in overall energy mix for 23 % in 2025 and 31 % in 2050. Nevertheless, the total percentage of renewable energy in the total energy mix only reaches 13 % in 2018 [7]. It shows that the use of renewable energy in Indonesia is still relatively low. Moreover, the high dependency on fossil fuels would give a negative impact on the environment. Therefore, it requires intensive action to accelerate the development of renewable energy use in Indonesia.

Indonesia is tropical energy, which becomes the largest palm oil producer in the world [8]. In 2017, Indonesia had produced Crude Palm Oil (CPO) of more than 34 million tons [9]. With the enormous source of palm oil, it can be utilized for producing biofuel as an alternative fuel in Indonesia [10].

Numerous studies reveal that palm oil can be converted into biofuel through catalytic cracking reaction [11–20]. Moreover, a study was shown that palm oil can give the best result compared to the others source for biofuel production [11]. The catalytic cracking reaction can be carried out through fixed bed reactor [14, 16, 17, 20] or Fluid Catalytic Cracking (FCC) technology [11–13, 21, 22]. From both catalytic cracking processes, FCC could give a more compatible product with the existing fossil-derived fuel.

A modern FCC system comprises some components, such as reactor, regenerator, stripper, etc. The reactor becomes the primary component in the FCC system because the catalytic cracking reactions take place inside the reactor [23]. A complex mechanism is involved in the reactor during the catalytic cracking reaction process. The cracking reaction process will produce various and complex substances. Thus, there is a well-known strategy that can be used to estimate the cracking reaction process called lump kinetic model [24]. In the beginning, the kinetic lump model only consists of 3 lumps [25]. Then, some researchers had proposed the others lump kinetic model with a higher number of lump, such as 4 lump [26], 5 lump [27, 28], 6 lump [24, 29–31], and 10 lump [32].

Besides the complexity of the reactions, the flow field phenomena, which occur inside the reactor, are even more complex. The flow inside the reactor involves multiphase flow, which consists of gas, feed vapor, and catalyst particles. The understanding of the flow phenomena is very crucial because the flow would affect the effectiveness of the reactions inside the reactor, especially in the injecting zone. CFD simulation could be a good way to estimate and describe the flow phenomena inside the reactor. Various CFD study intended to describe the phenomena inside the reactor was conducted, including the effect of the nozzle direction variation [33, 34] and the variation of the superficial velocity of the lifting fluid [35]. Various studies prefer to use the Eulerian-Eulerian (E-E) multiphase flow model to simulate the flow field inside the reactor due to its relatively low computational cost [36]. Some studies had also combined the E-E model with various kinetic lump models [36] to predict the yield product.

Despite the ability of the CFD simulation for providing detailed information on the flow field and the cracking reaction inside the reactor, it required an extremely high computational cost. On the other hand, process optimization, process control [37], and real-time monitoring in every component of the FCC system are very necessary. The model accuracy is very crucial to performing process optimization in the FCC system [38]. Therefore, it requires another technique that could give a lower computational cost. A combination of the model mechanism based on simplified structure-oriented lumping (SOL) and CatBoost machine learning model had been presented [38]. The model can reduce the computational cost from 20 hours to be only a minute with an accurate result. The other strategy was proposed through a CFD simulation based on Equivalent Reactor

Network (ERN) [39]. The model could give a more accurate result than a simple plug flow model. But with a lower computational cost than conventional CFD simulation.

FCC technology had been developed extensively. The first generation of the commercial FCC only consists of riser reactor and regenerator [40]. Afterward, a technology called R2R resid FCC is designed by Total corporation. This system uses a two-stage of regenerator, which could give a better combustion process of the coke and restore the catalyst activation level faster [41]. However, the structure of the FCC system with two stages of regenerator would be more complex than the system with only one stage regenerator. Hence, several studies were conducted to enhance the single-stage regenerator that can give a similar performance to the double-stage regenerator with a simpler structure [42]. One is enhancing the single-stage regenerator by reducing the back mixing which occurs inside the regenerator. It is found out that utilizing a baffle inside the regenerator, called Crosse grid for fluidized bed reactor, could significantly reduce the axial back mixing phenomena [42]. Moreover, the so-called «RegenMax» technology, which utilizes a «layer of corrugated packing internal», could reduce the solid back mixing inside the regenerator [43, 44]. Vienna Technology University had developed a pilot plant FCC with a unique structure that places the reactor inside the regenerator. The benefit of the configuration is less space requirement and the heat produced from the regenerator can be utilized to increase the reactor temperature [45]. The other innovation is the so-called High-Severity FCC (HS-FCC) which uses a downflow reactor, extremely high operational temperature, very short residence time, and high catalyst-to-oil ratio (CTO) [46]. This HS-FCC can avoid back-mixing in the reactor and can produce higher propylene and butene. Some researchers are also paying serious attention to the environmental issue, especially regarding the high carbon gas emission produced by the FCC system. Several strategies to reduce the carbon gas emission by FCC system had been proposed, such as the utilization of Oxy-Combustion technology [47], solvent-based carbon capture technology [48], and chemical-looping combustion [35] which are integrated into the FCC system. Among the recent development of FCC technology, most of the FCC systems use whether riser reactor or downer reactor only. Both reactors have its benefit and limitations.

A novel configuration of FCC system, which combines both riser and downer reactor, has been developed [49]. The FCC system also includes the utilization of feed evaporator. Because this FCC system does not use an injector nozzle to inject the feed into the reactor, a feed evaporator is used to evaporate the feed before it enters the reactor. The system also utilized an internal circulation regenerator, which was proposed [45]. The novel FCC, however, includes several valves, which control the flow of the FCC system. These valves setting variations in the FCC system remain a black box and need to be explored. The objective of this paper is to investigate the effect of the valve setting variation on the airflow distribution of the FCC system. This study aims to investigate the hydrodynamics characteristic of the novel FCC system and to investigate how the variation of the several control valve of the system would affect the flow distribution in the system. This study will perform through experimental study and acausal modeling.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fluid catalytic cracking

FCC becomes a major technology that is used to produce fuel in the world [40]. In General, the FCC system scheme can be simply described in **Fig. 1**.

Reactor is the main component in the FCC system in which the catalytic cracking reaction process is carried out. According to the flow direction, the reactor can be divided into two types, i. e., up flow type reactor (riser) and downflow reactor (downer).

Generally, the Feed, the material that would undergo catalytic cracking, is injected into the reactor in the form of droplets by using several nozzle injectors. Afterward, the feed droplets will be evaporated immediately after being in contact with high-temperature catalyst particles, which are dispersed with the lifting fluid. The catalytic cracking reaction process carried out along the reactor will produce various substances including coke particles. Some of the resulting coke particles will be deposited on the catalyst surface which will reduce the catalyst activation level [23], known as the spent catalyst. Therefore, the spent catalyst particles and the rest of the coke particles

would be separated from the vapor product into the regenerator. The coke particles would be burned inside the regenerator. Therefore, the deposited coke on the catalyst particles will be removed and the regenerated catalyst particles are ready to use for the next catalytic cracking reaction.

Fig. 1. General FCC scheme

2. 2. Experimental Methodology

2. 2. 1. FCC Proto X3

Ahmad Indra Research Group Universitas Indonesia (AIR-GROUP) has developed a bench-scale FCC system called FCC Proto X3. The ProtoX3 is designed with small reactor size. The reactor comprises two sections, i.e., the downer and riser reactor section. Unlike the existing FCC, which uses nozzle to inject the feed into the riser [50], FCC proto X3 does not use a nozzle to inject the feed. The use of the nozzle injector is ineffective because of the small size of the reactor's diameter, which could potentially increase the collision between the feed droplet and the reactor wall. Instead, this FCC system is provided by a falling film evaporator. The evaporator is used to evaporate the feed before it enters the reactor sections. The schematic diagram and photograph of FCC Proto X3 are shown in Fig. 2, a, b respectively. In addition, the liquid product resulting from the FCC Proto X3 is shown in Fig. 2, c.

The FCC system uses Liquid Petroleum gas (LPG) as a fuel and uses a blower to supply the airflow in the regenerator. Nitrogen gas is used as the lifting fluid in the system. Several valves are used in the FCC system to adjust the air supply and the nitrogen gas. The heat generated from the combustion in the regenerator will be used to heat the Nitrogen gas in the Nitrogen preheater section, to heat catalyst particles in the catalyst reheater sections, evaporate the feed in the feed evaporator, and provide thermal energy for the catalytic cracking reaction inside the downer reactor section. The air supply from the blower is divided into two directions, i.e., air supply for combustion in the regenerator and air supply for driving the spent catalyst to the regenerator. The gas nitrogen flow is also divided into two directions, i.e., the flow, which goes towards the riser reactor section, and the flow, which goes towards the downer reactor section. The former flow will create a low pressure, which sucks, and drive the regenerated catalyst particles passing through the catalyst reheater section toward the downer reactor section. Eventually, the former and the latter flow will intersect at a junction and flows toward the riser reactor section. After the reaction is carried out and the vapor product is formed, the spent catalyst will be separated through a cyclone separator. The vapor product will then move to the condenser to separate the non-condensable gas and the liquid product. Since the adjustment of the air supply in the FCC system is necessary, it becomes the main reason why the objective of this paper is to investigate the effect of the valve setting variation on the airflow distribution of the FCC system.

2. 2. 2. Measurement system

Several parameters are measured in the FCC Proto X3 including pressure, temperature, and flow rate of airflow. The flow rate of the airflow can be calculated from the measured velocity of the airflow and the cross-section area of the flow. The flow velocity is measured by using several air speed pitot tubes connected to the MPXV-7002DT Module. The other device used to measure the flow velocity is an anemometer, which has been modified to be able to measure a flow velocity in a tube. The inlet velocity of the air supply from the blower is measured by using an anemometer. The outlet velocity at both flue gas outlet and vapor product outlet is also measured by using an anemometer. Whereas the flow velocity inside the system at several points is measured by using the pitot tube. The pressure of the flow is measured by using a pressure transducer. The temperature at several points is measured by using K-type thermocouple. The measurement device is connected to RASPBERRY-Pi4 as a data acquisition device and microcontroller.

There are several notes for this measurement system. There are several limitations to using the pitot tube to measure the velocity of the airflow inside the tube. Some factors may affect the accuracy of the measurement such as misalignment between the flow direction and the pitot tube's hole, the flow which has not fully developed, unstable voltage, and other factors that can give noise to the data measurement process. Regardless, the measurement device used in the FCC Proto X3 can still give a reasonable measurement result.

2. 2. 3. Test Scheme

The experiment is carried out in cold test experiment conditions. The cold test experiment had also been carried out by some researchers to investigate the hydrodynamics [34]. Thus, there will not any combustion reaction inside the regenerator or catalytic cracking reaction in the reactor. Moreover, because there is no vapor product during the experiment, the nitrogen flow, as designed as a lifting fluid, is substituted by using an atmospheric airflow supplied by using a blower. The experiment also does not include any catalyst particles. Therefore, the experiment only focuses on the hydrodynamics of the flow in the system. The experiment is intended to investigate the effect of the various valve opening variation on the hydrodynamics of the FCC system. As shown in **Fig. 2, a**, there are six valves in the system, including the valve of air supply for combustion in the regenerator (valve 1), the valve of air supply for driving the spent catalyst to the regenerator (valve 2), the valve of the lifting fluid flow to the riser section (valve 3), and the valve at the particle flow section of the cyclone separator 2 (CS 2) where the spent catalyst is separated from the vapor product (valve 5). All of the six valves are varied with five combination schemes as shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1
Several test scheme in the experiment

Test Scheme	Valve 1 (Air supply for combustion in regenerator)	Valve 2 (Regenerated catalyst channel towards regenerator)	Valve 3 (Lifting fluid toward riser reactor)	Valve 4 (Lifting fluid toward downer reactor)	Valve 5 (Particle flow at CS 2)
TS 1 (All valve open)	100 % Open	100 % Open	100 % Open	100 % Open	100 % Open
TS 2 (Valve 5 closed)	100 % Open	100 % Open	100 % Open	100 % Open	Closed
TS 3 (Flow through regenerator)	Opening variation (25 %, 50 %, 75 %, 100 %)	Opening variation (25 %, 50 %, 75 %, 100 %)	Closed	Closed	Closed
TS 4 (Flow through reactor)	Closed	Closed	Opening variation (25 %, 50 %, 75 %, 100 %)	Opening variation (25 %, 50 %, 75 %, 100 %)	Closed
TS 5 (Flow through both reactor and regenerator)	100 % Open	Opening variation (25 %, 50 %, 75 %, 100 %)	Opening variation (25 %, 50 %, 75 %, 100 %)	100 % Open	Closed

2. 3. Calculation Model

2. 3. 1. Hydrodynamics model calculation

Hydrodynamics characteristics of the FCC Proto X3 system were also estimated by using atomic model. The atomic model concept is adopted from the concept of modeling on the atomic scale where the characteristic of each component of a system can be described [51]. The atomic terminology is also introduced in [52].

Estimation of the Hydrodynamics characteristics in the atomic model including the flow-rate distribution and pressure drop of the system at each section. The atomic model of FCC Proto X3 system is built by using the open-source software OpenModelica. The atomic model can model the complex FCC Proto X3 system through several class objects. Therefore, the characteristic of each component can be conceived more straightforwardly [51]. Afterward, each of the component's subclass will be connected by using a connector subclass provided in the OpenModelica.

By using the connector subclass, every component's class will form a system that satisfies the conservation principle [51].

The class objects, which built the FCC Proto X3 system model, comprise pipe, elbow, Tees junction, valve, cyclone, and regenerator. Each of the class objects can be used to define more than one component with different parameters, such as different lengths, diameter, materials, etc.

Pressure drop due to the major loss in the pipe can be estimated by using (1). Whereas the minor head loss presented at the valve, elbow, reducer, and Tees junction is calculated through (2):

$$h_{L\ major} = f \frac{L}{D_h} \frac{v^2}{2g}, \quad (1)$$

$$h_{L\ minor} = K_L \frac{v^2}{2g}, \quad (2)$$

where D_h is the hydraulic diameter, f is the friction factor, L is the length of the pipe, and V is the average velocity of the flow. The value of f depends on the surface roughness of the material and the Reynolds Number of the flow. The value of f can be estimated by using (3) [53]:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{f}} = -1.8 \log \left[\left(\frac{\varepsilon/D_h}{3.7} \right)^{1.11} + \frac{6.9}{\text{Re}} \right], \quad (3)$$

where ε is the relative surface roughness of the pipe wall. The value of the minor head loss in each component depends on the loss constants value K_L . The value K_L strictly depends on the geometrical aspect of the components. The K_L value of valve, reducer/divergent channel, tees junction, and elbow in this study is obtained from the reference [54]. Eventually, the pressure drop at every component can be calculated by using (4):

$$\Delta p = \gamma \left[\left(\frac{V_{out}^2}{2g} - \frac{V_{in}^2}{2g} \right) + (z_{out} - z_{in}) + (h_{L\ major} + h_{L\ minor}) \right], \quad (4)$$

where γ is the specific weight of fluid and z is the height position relative to the predetermined datum and respectively. The subscript *in* and *out* refer to the inlet and the outlet section of any component. The pressure drop at the cyclone separator can be estimated by using (5). V_{in} which is the flow velocity at the cyclone's inlet and N_H is the number of velocity head. The value N_H can be calculated through (6) [55]:

$$\Delta p_{cyclone} = \frac{1}{2} \rho V_{in}^2 N_H, \quad (5)$$

$$N_H = c_1 \frac{ab}{D_e^2} + c_2 \frac{h_b}{D} + c_3 \frac{h_c}{D} + c_4 \frac{S}{D}. \quad (6)$$

The value of a , b , D , and D_e in (6) can be described from the cyclone geometry as shown in **Fig. 3**, while the value of $C1$ to $C4$ are 14.8587, -0.6984 , -0.4841 , and 0.5738 respectively [55].

To ensure that the code and the algorithm of the FCC Proto X3 are appropriate, the number of the variables and the equation should be the same. The OpenModelica software provides the check-model feature to ensure that the number of variables and number of equations are the same. Such a feature can also give a warning if there is an error in the syntax. There are 687 equations and 687 variables in the model, which indicates that the code and the algorithm of the FCC Proto X3 system atomic model have been correct mathematically. The calculation algorithm of the Atomic Model is shown in **Fig. 4**.

Fig. 3. Cyclone Geometry Model [55]

Fig. 4. Calculation Algorithm of the Atomic Model of FCC Proto X3

3. Results and Discussion

The effect of the opening variation of valve 5 on the system is observed through the first and the second test scheme as shown in **Table 1**. The comparison of the measurement result is shown in **Fig. 5, 6**:

Fig. 5. Comparison of the measured velocity between the first and the second test scheme

Fig. 6. Measured pressure at the inlet section in the first and the second test scheme

According to **Fig. 5**, there is a significantly different in the measured velocity at the outlet product section between the first and the second test scheme. The measured outlet product velocity in the second experiment scheme is higher than the measured outlet product velocity in the first experiment scheme. The opened valve 5 reduces the flow rate flowing toward the outlet product section. The lower side of the CS 2 is connected with a channel toward the regenerator. At that channel flow, a nozzle creates a high-speed and low-pressure zone which will suck the flow at the cyclone separator into the regenerator. Valve 5 is designed to control the sucking effect between the low-pressure zone and the CS 2. When valve 5 opens, some of the flow from the CS 2 will be sucked into the regenerator. Thus, it will be much flowrate flowing through the regenerator toward the outlet flue gas. Moreover, the open valve 5 also creates a slightly higher measured pressure at the inlet section as shown in **Fig. 6**. When valve 5 opens some flow is sucked into the regenerator, which will create vortex flow due to the geometrical effect. Therefore, it will raise the pressure drop of the overall system as indicated from the measured pressure at the inlet section in the first test scheme.

The consideration of the valve 5 opening is very important, especially when the FCC system is running and includes the combustion reaction in the regenerator and catalytic cracking reaction in the reactor. The resulting vapor product from the cracking reaction will flow through the CS 2

to separate the spent catalyst particles and coke particles. The suction produced by the lower-pressure zone at the channel connected to the lower side of the CS 2 will help suck the particles separated at the CS 2. If the valve 5 opening level is too small, it may cause reduce the sucking effect on the catalyst particles and cause many particles to escape with the vapor product. On the other hand, if the valve opening level is too high, it may cause too high suction effect which not only sucks the particles but also sucks some of the resulting vapor product and reduces the final yield product. Therefore, it is very important to consider the appropriate opening level of valve 5 that could give the optimum suction effect.

In test scheme 3, the higher opening level of valve 1 and valve 2 will reduce the measured pressure at the inlet sections as shown in **Fig. 7, a**. Otherwise, the measured velocity at the inlet sections is increased as both valves are set at a higher opening level. These indicate that the higher opening level of both valves will reduce the head loss of the flow in the system.

Fig. 7. Effect of valve 1 and valve 2 opening level variation on: *a* – pressure at inlet sections; *b* – airflow velocity at inlet section; *c* – velocity at the channel toward regenerator; *d* – velocity at the flue gas outlet in the test scheme 3

According to **Fig. 7, b, d**, the change in the measured velocity of the flow at the flue gas outlet sections has a similar trend to the measured velocity at the inlet sections. This similar trend indicates the continuity of the flow because there is no flow toward the reactor and the product outlet. Note that the difference value between the measured velocity of the flow at the inlet and the flue gas outlet is caused by the different sizes of the channel diameter.

This scheme only divides the airflow into two directions i.e., airflow through valve 1 for combustion air supply and flow to the channel toward the regenerator through valve 2. **Fig. 7, c** shows that the velocity of the flow at the channel toward the regenerator is increased as the opening level of valve 2 increases. Otherwise, the higher level of valve 1 will reduce the velocity of the flow at the channel towards the regenerator and increase the flow for the combustion's air supply.

The consideration of the opening level of both valve 1 and valve 2 is very important to control the combustion process inside the regenerator. It is necessary to obtain the optimum air-fuel ratio (AFR) for the combustion process inside the regenerator so that the opening level of valve 1 can be adjusted appropriately. On the other hand, the opening level of valve 2 should also be adjusted appropriately to suck and drive the spent catalyst as mentioned previously. Therefore, it is required to adjust the appropriate opening level of both valve 1 and valve 2.

In test scheme 4, it is obtained that the higher opening level of valve 4 leads to reducing the measured pressure and the measured velocity at the inlet sections as shown in **Fig. 8, a, b**. The lower pressure at the inlet sections indicates that the pressure loss of the flow is decreased as the opening level of valve 4 increases.

Fig. 8. Effect of valve 3 and valve 4 opening level variation on: *a* – pressure at inlet sections; *b* – airflow velocity at inlet section, and; *c* – velocity at the product outlet in the test scheme 4

The airflow is not allowed to flow enter neither the reactor downer reactor sections nor the riser reactor sections. It is because the presence of any oxygen in the reactor should be avoided during the catalytic cracking reactions occur. However, because there are no catalytic cracking reactions included in this experiment, let's use air supplied from the blower. This experiment scheme 4 only allows the airflow flows toward the reactor without any airflow toward the regenerator. It is obtained that the higher opening level of valve 4 will increase the velocity of the flow at the product outlet section as shown in **Fig. 8, c**. In addition, the velocity of the airflow decreased significantly as valve 3 closed. Moreover, the change in the velocity of the airflow at the product outlet also has a similar trend to the change in the velocity at the inlet section. It indicates the continuity of the flow also.

The effect of the opening level of valve 4 plays a vital role to control the supply of the lifting fluid to the reactor. If the combustion in the generator were included, the amount of the lifting fluid flowing through valve 4 will affect the temperature distribution along the downer reactor. It is because the lifting fluid, which passes through the catalyst reheater section, also supplies thermal energy to the downer reactor section. Therefore, the higher opening level of valve 4 will raise the amount of the flow of the lifting fluid containing high thermal energy toward the downer reactor.

Nevertheless, when the amount of the lifting fluid toward the downer reactor is increased, the amount of the lifting fluid, which flows directly toward the riser reactor, is decreased. Consequently, too small amount of lifting fluid may not provide enough energy to drive the vapor product and the particle catalyst through the riser reactors sections.

In the test scheme 5, the higher opening level of the valve 2 creates a higher velocity and a lower pressure at the inlet section as shown in **Fig. 9, a, b**. That indicates that the higher opening level of the valve 2 will reduce the overall head loss of the system.

When valve 2 is closed completely, the variation of the opening level of valve 3 gives a significant effect on the measured velocity at the product outlet section which shows a similar trend to the test scheme 4.

As shown in **Fig. 9, d**, the velocity at the product outlet sections is decreased as the opening level of valve 2 increases. The higher opening level of valve 2 leads to an increase in the amount of flow toward the regenerator and flowing out through the flue gas outlet. Consequently, it will reduce the amount of flow toward the reactor. Therefore, it will also reduce the velocity of the flow at the product outlet section as shown in **Fig. 9, d**. In addition, the velocity of the flow at the product outlet is also decreased significantly when valve 3 is completely closed. On the other hand, the decreasing amount of the flow toward the reactor will increase the amount of the airflow toward the outlet flue gas outlet as represented by the measured velocity at the outlet flue gas in **Fig. 9, c**.

Fig. 9. Effect of valve 2 and valve 3 opening level variation on: *a* – pressure at inlet sections; *b* – airflow velocity at inlet section; *c* – airflow velocity at the flue gas outlet; *d* – velocity at the product outlet in the test scheme 5

During operation, the lifting fluid plays a vital role in driving the resulting vapor product and the catalyst particles toward the CS 2 separator. If the opening level of valve 3 is too small, it may cause too low lifting fluid flow which is unavailable to drive all catalyst particles to the separator optimally. Hence, there will much catalyst particles left inside the riser reactor. Moreover, the amount of the lifting fluid also determines the effectivity of the condensation process of the vapor product at the heat exchanger. If the flow rate of the lifting fluid is too low, the condensation process in the heat exchanger will not be effective due to the low heat transfer coefficient. Therefore, it is required to adjust the appropriate opening level of valve 3 to provide an optimum flow of the lifting fluid. On the other hand,

3. 1. Atomic model of hydrodynamic of the FCC system

The atomic model of the hydrodynamic characteristic of the FCC Proto X3 system is developed. The important thing that needs to be estimated in the FCC system is how the valve opening variation will affect the distribution of the flow in the system. The flow that is divided into several channels and reconnected to a certain point will have the same pressure drop [54]. This basic principle is used to estimate the flow distribution in the FCC system through the atomic model. To validate the model, a similar condition with test scheme 3 is used. In addition, the measured velocity of the flow at the inlet section will be used as the input variable for the atomic model.

The effect of the opening level of valve 1 and valve 2 on the distribution of the airflow is shown in **Fig. 10, a**. It is obtained that the velocity of the flow at the channel toward the regenerator is increased as the opening level of valve 2 increases. It means that the estimated velocity at the channel toward the regenerator by the atomic model has a similar trend to the experimental result. The velocity at the channel toward the regenerator is also increased significantly when the opening level of the valve is reduced. However, there is a cut-off point of the velocity at the channel toward the regenerator when the opening level of valve 2 is open 3/4 of its fully open as shown in **Fig. 10, a**. The valve 1, which is completely closed, will create a higher pressure drop in the system, thus reducing the amount of the airflow supplied by the blower.

The velocity of the airflow at the flue gas outlet estimated by the atomic model is shown in **Fig. 10, b**. It is obtained that the velocity at the flue gas outlet is increased as the greater

opening level of either valve 1 or valve 2. It indicates that there is a greater amount of airflow flowing toward the regenerator, which agrees with the experimental results. In addition, the continuity of the airflow resulting from the atomic model is satisfied as to the flow rate at the inlet section and the flue gas outlet are equal as shown in Fig. 10, c. Therefore, the atomic model can predict the flow distribution of the system by satisfying the continuity of the flow. Moreover, it can be seen from Fig. 7, d, 10, b. that the change of the velocity at the flue gas outlet has an identical trend to the experimental result. Nevertheless, there is a significantly different in the velocity at the flue gas outlet quantitatively between the atomic model estimation result and the experimental result. The measured flue gas outlet velocity from the experiment shows a greater value than the estimated one from the atomic model. It also indicates that the result from the measurement in the experiment does not meet the mass conservation of the flow. From several factors, measurement error considers being the main reason for this problem. It indicates that the use of the anemometer to measure velocity at the flue gas outlet is inaccurate. Moreover, the non-fully developed flow can also affect the accuracy of the measurement results. Despite this, the result from both experiment and the atomic model can provide qualitative information on how the variation of the opening level of the valves of the system affects the hydrodynamics characteristic of the system, especially the flow distribution.

Fig. 10. Atomic model estimation on: *a* – airflow velocity at the channel toward the regenerator; *b* – airflow velocity at the flue gas outlet; *c* – the airflow flowrate at several locations

There are several limitations in this study. The use of the pitot tube to measure the velocity of the airflow inside the tube may result in several problems. Factors such as misalignment between the flow direction and the pitot tube's hole, unsteady voltage, and other sources of noise can affect the accuracy of the measurement. For future research, it is recommended to use more advanced measurement devices to obtain more accurate velocity data. Additionally, conducting CFD simulations of the flow inside the reactor, cyclone separator, and regenerator can provide detailed information about the flow field inside these components. CFD simulations can complement the experimental data and help develop a comprehensive model of the FCC Proto X3 system.

4. Conclusions

The hydrodynamic characteristic of the flow in a novel FCC system is investigated. The effect of the variation of the valve opening level in the FCC system on the flow distribution is analyzed through several test schemes. The atomic model is also used to estimate the effect of the valve opening level on the flow distribution in the FCC system. It is obtained that valve 2 which controls

the flow at the channel toward the regenerator is essential due to its role in controlling the air supply combustion process in the regenerator and driving the spent catalyst particles to the regenerator. If the opening level of valve 2 is set too small, it may cause much of the catalyst particles cannot to be sucked in and driven into the regenerator. On the other hand, if the opening level of valve 5 is set too high, it may create a strong suction that can suck not only the spent catalyst particles from the CS 2 but also will suck and drive some of the vapor product to the regenerator. Valve 3 is responsible for controlling the flow toward the riser reactor directly. Later, it is responsible for supplying the lifting fluid to support the catalytic cracking reaction at the riser sections. If the opening level of valve 3 is set to small, it cannot provide enough amount of lifting fluid to support the catalytic cracking reaction at the riser reactor sections. Valve 4 contributes to controlling the lifting fluid to the downer reactor. Later, it will also be responsible for supplying thermal energy from the high-temperature particle catalyst to the reactor. The estimation result obtained from the atomic model shows a similar trend to the experiment result. it implies that the atomic model can be used to estimate the effect of the various opening valve variation on the hydrodynamics characteristic, especially the flow distribution, in the FCC system.

Conflicts of interest

The author declares that he has no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on reasonable request.

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